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Interactions of vitamin- and mineral-containing dietary supplements with medications

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Introduction: Vitamin- and mineral-containing supplements are usually the most frequently used dietary supplements among adults. Oftentimes, they are used concomitantly with medicines. Aim: The aim of this work was to summarize some of the most important interactions of vitamin- and mineral-containing dietary supplements with frequently used medications. Methods: The data on the interactions of interest were obtained from scientific literature databases (PubMed, Google Scholar, ScienceDirect) using theme-relevant search strings. Results: Vitamins in the interactions spotlight include vitamin D, folic acid, vitamins C, E and B12. Chronic use of corticosteroid drugs may require vitamin D supplementation as it decreases vitamin D serum concentrations. In addition, vitamin D supplementation may increase the rates of absorption of aluminium from aluminium-containing medicines raising the risk of aluminium toxicity. Folic acid supplements' kinetics may be altered by multiple medicines and vice versa. Medicines of interest in this case are some anticonvulsants (phenytoin, carbamazepine, valproic acid), antimetabolites (methotrexate) and pancreatic enzymes. Excessive intakes of vitamin C and E might decrease the efficacy of anticoagulant medicines. Vitamin C is hypothesized to interfere with the effects of some antineoplastics. Regardless of their mechanism of action, long-term use of medicines that increase the pH in the stomach (e.g. antacids, H₂ blockers, proton-pump inhibitors) may negatively affect the pH-dependent absorption of vitamin B12 and therefore require supplemental vitamin B12. Among minerals, absorption of iron is susceptible to a decrease in absorption if administered together with pH-increasing medicines. In general, several minerals tend to affect the absorption of some medicines by chelation. Namely, calcium and magnesium supplements form complex salts with tetracyclines and fluoroquinolones, as well as bisphosphonates and possibly levothyroxine, decreasing their absorption and, consequently, their efficacy. Similarly, iron can bind tetracyclines, fluoroquinolones, levothyroxine, but also digoxin, levodopa and methylodopa interfering with their effects. Conclusion: Healthcare providers should hold adequate competencies to inform patients on the possibilities of vitamins and minerals from their supplements interacting with their prescribed medications and advise them on proper interactions-avoidance strategies. This can decrease the risks of patients being negatively affected by supplements-medicines interactions and, in turn, better their therapeutic outcomes.

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